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The relational digital divide: psychosocial dimensions of digital exclusion in disadvantaged neighbourhoods

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ABSTRACT

This article examines how residents of structurally marginalised neighbourhoods navigate everyday information and digitalised institutional communication. Drawing on fifty-two semi-structured interviews and an action-group discussion with women living in six disadvantaged neighbourhoods in the Czech Republic, the study uses reflexive thematic analysis to explore how information is interpreted, shared and emotionally managed in contexts of institutional mistrust. The findings show that the digital divide operates less as a technological gap than as a relational and affective phenomenon. Digital communication was often experienced as overwhelming, ambiguous or threatening. As a result, information was navigated collectively through relational infrastructures—neighbours, family members and trusted social workers—who helped contain anxiety and translate institutional messages. Social workers emerged as key actors in mediating the emotional burdens of digitalised welfare communication. The article argues for a psychosocial reconceptualisation of the digital divide and underscores the importance of relationship-based, emotionally attuned social work.

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Introduction

Across Europe and elsewhere, the accelerating digitalisation of welfare, education and health systems has reshaped how citizens communicate with institutions. In this article, digitalisation refers to the institutional shift from face-to-face and paper-based communication towards digital-first systems. In the Czech Republic, this transformation intensified after 2000 through the expansion of e-government infrastructures and electronic case management, altering everyday social work practice and client–institution interaction (Bražinová & Caletková, 2024; Kähönen et al., 2023). Although often framed as enhancing efficiency and accessibility, digitalisation is experienced far more ambivalently in structurally disadvantaged neighbourhoods, where institutional mistrust, spatial stigma and poverty shape everyday life (Mikulcová, 2025). Opening an email from school or receiving a notification from a welfare office may provoke shame, anxiety or fear of

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misunderstanding. In such contexts, the digital divide concerns not only devices or skills but emotional safety, relational support and institutional holding.

Psychodynamic social work highlights how emotional life is shaped through relationships and how practitioners provide containment and meaning-making under conditions of uncertainty (Howe, 1995; Lanyado & Horne, 2009; Ruch, 2005). In disadvantaged neighbourhoods—where public institutions are often experienced as inconsistent, surveillant or hostile—social workers may become key ‘holding figures’ capable of transforming overwhelming digital or bureaucratic information into something manageable. This dynamic is particularly visible among women, who carry much of the emotional and organisational labour of navigating welfare, education and health systems, labour that is often gendered, invisible and insufficiently recognised (Mikulcová, 2025).

Territorial stigmatisation (Wacquant, 2007, 2008) produces not only material exclusion but an internalised expectation of disbelief or scrutiny, contributing to epistemic precarity—a chronic uncertainty about what is true, whom to trust and how institutional messages should be interpreted. Psychosocial scholarship shows how such socio-spatial conditions shape expectations of rejection and self-silencing within community life (Cooper & Lousada, 2005; Hoggett, 2009; Hollway, 2013). Consistent with these insights, participants described digital systems not as neutral tools but as objects imbued with meanings of surveillance, failure and shame—what Bollas (1987) calls ‘the intrusive object’.

Despite growing evidence of the emotional complexity surrounding digitalised welfare systems (Eubanks, 2018; Gillingham & Humphreys, 2010), little research examines how information is navigated and emotionally processed within disadvantaged neighbourhoods, or how relational infrastructures—neighbours, children, community workers and social workers—function as alternative holding environments. This study addresses these gaps by exploring how residents of six structurally marginalised neighbourhoods in the Czech Republic make sense of everyday information.

Anchored in psychodynamic and relationship-based traditions, this article conceptualises the digital divide as a relational and affective phenomenon shaped by structural inequality and institutional practices. Drawing on concepts of containment and holding (Bion, 1962; Winnicott, 1960), the analysis shows how punitive or opaque forms of institutional communication undermine confidence in digital engagement. Avoidance of digital platforms or reliance on trusted others thus emerges not as ignorance but as a protective response to anticipated shame or misrecognition (Klein, 1946). The analysis deepens understanding of how social work mediates digital engagement within emotionally charged environments.

The digital divide as a psychosocial and relational phenomenon: a psychodynamic–systemic framework for contemporary social work practice

The digital divide is increasingly understood as a multidimensional form of exclusion that extends beyond access or technical capacity alone. Park (2022) conceptualises digital exclusion as deeply intertwined with broader processes of social exclusion, emphasising that inequalities in digital participation reflect and reinforce structural disadvantage. The COVID-19 pandemic further exposed these dynamics, revealing how data gaps, digital

deprivation and institutional reliance on digital infrastructures intensified social vulnerability and unevenly distributed risks during periods of crisis (Naudé & Vinuesa, 2021).

Research on digital transformation in public services shows how these processes generate new forms of marginalisation. Digital systems often presuppose stability, literacy and confidence that people living in marginalised communities do not consistently possess, thereby limiting inclusion despite formal access to services (Djatkiko et al., 2025). Under conditions of uncertainty, such environments may provoke withdrawal rather than engagement. Ogbo-Gebhardt (2025) demonstrate that digital communication can trigger information avoidance when institutional messages are perceived as overwhelming, ambiguous or risky. As Gherlone (2025) argues, digital environments are embedded in affective atmospheres that shape orientations of trust, anxiety or retreat. Together, this literature situates the digital divide as a social, institutional and affective process.

Understanding the digital divide solely through material or educational lenses, however, obscures its psychosocial character. Access, skill and outcome disparities are inseparable from the relational, emotional and organisational contexts in which digital practices unfold. From a social work perspective informed by psychodynamic and systemic thinking, the digital divide is not only a question of technological distribution but also an expression of anxiety, trust, identity and relationship to authority.

Psychodynamic approaches draw attention to the emotional and unconscious processes shaping relationships to digital environments. Klein (1946) and Bion (1962) describe how individuals confronted with uncertainty or overload may mobilise defence mechanisms—avoidance, projection and splitting—to manage anxiety. The contemporary digital landscape, saturated with contradictory and affectively charged stimuli, readily activates such defences. Research on information overload supports this view, showing how overwhelming information flows can lead to digital avoidance (Soroya et al., 2021).

From this perspective, digital exclusion may arise not simply from a lack of skills but from anxiety about failure, exposure or loss of control. Digital technologies may evoke shame, inadequacy or fear of judgement, or become objects onto which distrust of institutions is projected. These dynamics resonate with Turkle's (2011) account of technologies as emotionally charged relational objects and Frosh's (2013) analysis of media environments as symbolic containers for anxieties about identity, recognition and power.

A further psychodynamic contribution is Winnicott's (1960) notion of the holding environment, which describes a relational context providing sufficient emotional containment and predictability for learning and autonomy. Digital environments, particularly under conditions of chronic social adversity, often fail to offer such holding. Without containment, digital systems may be experienced as intrusive or bewildering, prompting individuals to turn to trusted interpersonal relationships—family members, neighbours or social workers—for interpretive support. Technologies thus become embedded within established relational patterns rather than functioning as independent tools.

Group analytic and psychosocial theorists extend this analysis to collective life. Bion's (1961) theory of basic assumption groups shows how communities under stress may mobilise collective defences that inhibit engagement with anxiety-provoking practices. Obholzer and Roberts (1994) similarly demonstrate how organisations generate shared

narratives that stabilise cohesion while constraining adaptation. Phrases such as ‘the internet is dangerous’ or ‘it is safer to ask someone we know’ may therefore function as communal defence mechanisms that maintain identity while reinforcing digital exclusion. The digital divide, in this sense, is not merely an individual deficit but a phenomenon embedded in shared emotional life and defensive social structures.

Disadvantaged neighbourhoods as psychosocial landscapes of digital exclusion

Although the Czech Republic demonstrates high overall ICT penetration—approximately 85–90% of households report internet access and mobile phone ownership is nearly universal (Czech Statistical Office, 2023)—digital exclusion remains socially patterned. PAQ Research (2024) estimates that 17% of adults are digitally excluded and a further 16% are at risk. More than 600 socially excluded localities have been identified nationwide (GAC, 2015), inhabited by approximately 115,000 residents—characterised by concentrated poverty and low educational attainment; however, precise ICT penetration statistics for these areas are not systematically available. Available evidence nevertheless indicates significant barriers—characterised by concentrated poverty and low educational attainment; precise ICT penetration statistics for these areas are not systematically available. Pandemic-era research indicates that 10–20% of children in disadvantaged households lacked adequate devices for online schooling, with many families relying on shared smartphones or prepaid mobile data rather than stable broadband (PAQ Research, 2024).

Multidimensional measurement frameworks, such as the Internet Poverty Index (Internet Poverty Institute, 2022), conceptualise digital poverty beyond access by incorporating affordability, connection quality, digital skills, usage and online safety. According to the Index, 16,120 people in the Czech Republic—approximately 3% of the country’s total population—are classified as internet poor. Although not calculated specifically for socially excluded localities, its multidimensional logic situates this study within broader debates on digital poverty while highlighting dimensions that quantitative metrics alone cannot capture.

From a psychodynamic, socio-spatial and systemic perspective, the digital divide cannot be understood as a matter of individual competence or motivation. It unfolds within emotional, relational and organisational worlds shaped by place. Structurally disadvantaged neighbourhoods—often described as territories of advanced marginality—emerge from long-term disinvestment, territorial stigmatisation, spatial segregation and limited policy engagement (Wacquant, 2007, 2008). Such neighbourhoods are marked not only by reduced access to education, healthcare, employment, mobility and stable information infrastructures (e.g. Kähönen et al., 2023; Mikulcová, 2025) but also by institutional mistrust and cumulative histories of exclusion.

Within these settings, the relational character of the digital divide becomes especially pronounced. Information and technology do not arrive in neutral or benevolent ways; they are mediated through relationships that may be fragile, mistrustful or shaped by past failures of care (Mikulcová, 2025). Internalised territorial stigma influences expectations of disbelief and shapes whether uncertainty can be disclosed. Psychodynamic theory helps illuminate these dynamics: anxieties about exposure, shame and anticipated

judgement can make digital systems feel risky or unsafe (Frosh, 2013; Turkle, 2011). When institutions fail to provide attuned and comprehensible communication, they do not offer the basic holding environment that Winnicott (1960, 1965) describes as foundational for learning and exploration. Instead, bureaucratic procedures may be experienced as intrusive or overwhelming, requiring containment in Bion's (1962) sense.

These psychosocial pressures fall unevenly across the community. Women—particularly mothers and grandmothers—bear disproportionate responsibility for navigating welfare offices, schools, health systems and housing authorities, often acting as the primary interface between families and institutions (Lister, 2003). Yet their knowledge and credibility are frequently doubted, mirroring what Fricker (2007) identifies as testimonial injustice based on prejudicial social assumptions. They are expected to manage complex digital systems while absorbing the emotional turbulence of bureaucratic communication, labour that often proceeds without institutional recognition or support.

In this context, the digital divide becomes fundamentally relational and psychodynamic. It is shaped not only by gaps in access or skills, but by the absence of institutional attunement, stigma and mistrust. Digital systems become intrusive objects in Bollas's (1987) sense—objects that evoke anxiety and defensive responses—rather than straightforward resources for empowerment. Navigating the digital world therefore entails negotiating technological demands alongside the psychosocial legacy of structural exclusion. Understanding the digital divide in these settings therefore requires relationship-based, emotionally attuned social work.

Analytically, we distinguish three interrelated dimensions of the digital divide. First, the infrastructural dimension concerns material access to devices and stable connectivity (van Dijk, 2020). Second, the usage dimension refers to digital skills and the capacity to engage meaningfully with institutional platforms (Helsper, 2021). Third, and central to this study, is a relational—psychosocial dimension that shapes how digital systems are encountered within contexts of stigma, mistrust and institutional power. While analytically separable, these dimensions interact: limited access or skills may intensify anxiety and dependency, while experiences of misrecognition can undermine even formally available connectivity and competencies.

Methods

This study adopted a qualitative design to explore how residents of disadvantaged neighbourhoods make sense of everyday information and navigate digital and institutional communication. The approach was grounded in the principles of participatory social work research in which meaning is understood as co-constructed, affectively mediated, and embedded in social, spatial and organisational contexts.

The research proceeded in two interconnected stages. The first stage focused on everyday information practices: where residents turn for clarification, how they interpret and emotionally respond to institutional or digital messages, and how neighbourhood dynamics shape their engagement with information. The second stage created space for collaborative interpretation, enabling participants to revisit and refine emerging themes.

Fieldwork was carried out in six disadvantaged neighbourhoods in the Czech Republic, each publicly recognised as a disadvantaged neighbourhood. These areas are

characterised by long-term unemployment, limited educational opportunities, debt enforcement, insecure housing and persistent territorial stigma. The six neighbourhoods were selected from the Moravskoslezský kraj and Ústecký kraj, two regions consistently ranking among the most socially excluded in the Czech Republic according to the Index of Social Exclusion (Agency for Social Inclusion in Czechia, 2024). This composite index aggregates municipal-level indicators of unemployment, long-term benefit dependency, debt enforcement, educational attainment and housing precarity. In several municipalities within these regions, unemployment rates reach exceptionally high levels—reported in some cases at 80–85%—reflecting long-term detachment from the formal labour market and widespread reliance on welfare benefits. Educational disadvantage is similarly pronounced, with a substantial share of residents having only basic schooling and very limited progression to secondary or vocational qualifications (Agency for Social Inclusion for Czechia, 2023). Within these structurally disadvantaged regions, specific neighbourhoods were identified using residential segregation methodologies (Sýkora, 2023) to capture the highest spatial concentrations of socio-economic marginalisation at the sub-municipal level. All sites are urban or peri-urban post-industrial settings. While not statistically representative, they constitute analytically critical cases of concentrated marginalisation, supporting theoretical generalisation regarding relational dynamics of digital exclusion in comparable contexts.

Community centres and low-threshold organisations had been active in these neighbourhoods for several years and served as relationally attuned and trusted gateways for recruitment. Their presence was vital in communities marked by histories of institutional mistrust and where the appearance of outsiders can evoke anxiety or guardedness.

Twenty-six women took part in the study's first stage, each participating in two semi-structured interviews (fifty-two interviews in total). The study adopted a gender-focused sampling strategy. Women were deliberately recruited because preliminary field engagement and prior research indicated that they disproportionately carry responsibility for managing communication with schools, welfare offices and health institutions in the studied communities. In these neighbourhood contexts, women—particularly mothers and grandmothers—function as primary institutional mediators within households. The research therefore aimed to examine digital navigation as it is enacted by those most structurally positioned to perform this labour. This design does not assume that men are absent from institutional navigation, but rather focuses analytically on the gendered organisation of care and bureaucratic responsibility in marginalised settings (Lister, 2003). Participants were recruited through community workers and snowball sampling—strategies suited to relationally fragile environments and grounded in consent, trust and voluntariness. Most were mothers or grandmothers aged between their early twenties and early seventies and had lived in their neighbourhoods for between two and thirty-five years. To ensure confidentiality in small, socially visible communities, demographic information is presented only in aggregate.

Interviews explored participants' everyday information practices, their experiences with digitalised institutional communication, and the relational dynamics through which meaning-making takes place. The first interview invited participants to describe how they seek, verify, share or avoid information; how they navigate letters, emails or notifications from schools and welfare offices; and how stigma, past encounters or emotional discomfort shape their sense of what can safely be asked.

The second interview, usually held several weeks later, allowed participants to return to earlier themes, clarify meanings and reflect more deeply on moments of confusion, shame, worry or relational dependence. These follow-up conversations also enabled the researcher to check emerging interpretations and minimise the risk of imposing external meanings. Interviews were held in locations chosen for their relational safety—community centres, outdoor courtyards, or participants' homes. They ranged from thirty-five to one hundred and forty minutes, were audio-recorded with consent, and were transcribed verbatim.

After preliminary coding and thematic development, a second stage of data collection was conducted with a resident action group composed of seven women from one field site. Action groups—locally rooted, task-focused collectives supported by community workers (Ledwith, 2011)—provide both participatory insight and grounded local expertise. The group functioned as a peer-advisory body, reflecting on the preliminary themes, offering alternative readings and highlighting nuances not present in individual interviews. Where the one-to-one interviews illuminated personal and household-level information practices, the action-group discussion shed light on collective meaning-making: how information travels through networks, how digital communication intersects with neighbourhood conflict or stigma, and how women collectively interpret and respond to institutional demands.

Data were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019). The process involved repeated readings of transcripts, inductive and affect-sensitive coding, cross-neighbourhood comparison and iterative refinement of themes. Insights from the action-group discussion were woven into the later analytic stages to enhance validity, challenge researcher assumptions and deepen the emerging interpretations.

Ethical approval was granted by the Research Ethics Committee of University of Ostrava (2025), and the study adhered to the British Psychological Society's Code of Human Research Ethics (2010). Given the high visibility and small scale of the communities involved, ensuring anonymity and minimising harm were central concerns. Participants chose interview locations and were offered follow-up contact to clarify consent, withdraw material or reflect further on the emotional impact of participation.

The study is grounded in fifty-two interviews and one action-group discussion, the patterns identified offer important insights into the emotional and organisational dynamics shaping residents' everyday engagements with information in marginalised contexts, while remaining subject to limitations related to social desirability effects, the goal-oriented nature of interview-based data, and the non-generalisability of findings beyond comparable socio-spatial settings.

Results

Overall, the findings indicate that everyday engagements with information in disadvantaged neighbourhoods are primarily relational, affective, and embodied rather than individual or cognitively driven. Information circulates through dense social ties, producing conditions of epistemic precarity shaped by emotional contagion, uncertainty, and defensive communication practices, while digital technologies often intensify rather than alleviate these dynamics. In this context of institutional mistrust and testimonial injustice, social workers emerge as key relational figures providing epistemic containment and

interpretive support within a neighbourhood understood as a psychosocial and epistemic ecosystem shaped by structural disadvantage.

Information as a relational, collective and embodied practice

Participants consistently described information as something that circulates through relationships rather than through institutional channels. Knowledge moved across the neighbourhood through everyday encounters—conversations in hallways, voices called across balconies, or quick exchanges on the street. One participant described this simply: ‘The neighbours will tell me. That’s just how it works here’. (CP2) Others noted that the flow of information required almost no effort: ‘When I open the window, I already know what is going on’. (CP6)

Participants highlighted how rapidly rumours and emotional interpretations circulate. One observed: ‘Someone makes a conclusion, and then it spreads’. (CP9). The perceived lack of privacy intensified this dynamic: ‘They will find out. We are all here’. (CP6)

From a psychodynamic perspective, the neighbourhood operates simultaneously as a holding environment and a projective field. People often turn to one another for reassurance and containment, yet the same proximity amplifies anxieties and fuels the rapid mobilisation of defensive processes. What participants describe is not merely informal information exchange but a relational epistemic infrastructure embedded in the material and emotional proximity of the neighbourhood. Information here is inseparable from bodies, voices, and shared space; it is overheard, felt, and anticipated rather than deliberately sought. This embodied circulation enables rapid collective orientation, but it also renders information highly susceptible to affective amplification, projection, and misrecognition. In this sense, knowledge is not only shared but *co-experienced*, producing both solidarity and vulnerability.

The relational digital divide

Digital technologies, though widely owned, were experienced as emotionally threatening and unpredictable. Many participants described avoiding digital communication out of fear or shame. One explained: ‘I don’t comment on anything; I only read . . . I am afraid’. (CP1) Another said: ‘I don’t understand it, so I’d rather not even open it’. (CP5). Several noted that unread emails accumulated because they could not distinguish what mattered: ‘I have fifty emails, but I don’t know which ones are important’. (CP9)

Delegating digital tasks to others was common. One mother described her daughter as the primary interpreter of digital messages: ‘She brings me all the news’. (CP7) Another relied on a neighbour: ‘When I need to write something, I ask my neighbour—she writes it for me’. (CP15) Children often mediated communication with schools: ‘The kids translate the school messages for me; I no longer know what they want’. (CP13)

Participants reported moments of panic triggered by digital alerts: ‘My phone beeps and I’m startled, thinking it’s the school or the office again’. (CP3) These reactions reflect not incompetence but defensive withdrawal from environments experienced as potentially shaming, punitive or overwhelming. Digital systems often functioned psychodynamically as intrusive objects—evoking fear of mistakes, exposure or judgement.

Social media use followed emotional and relational lines. One participant said: ‘When I see someone is missing, I share it . . . that’s the least I can do’. (CP10) Another described consuming highly emotional content: ‘On TikTok they say only horrors . . . you get scared immediately’. (CP19) These patterns reveal that digital engagement is deeply affective, shaped by neighbourhood anxieties, relational trust and the need for resonance rather than accuracy.

The data suggest that the so-called ‘digital divide’ operates less as a technical gap and more as an affective and relational divide. Digital interfaces are not neutral tools but emotionally charged environments that activate fear of error, exposure, and institutional sanction. Delegation of digital tasks should therefore be understood not as dependency, but as a protective relational strategy that redistributes epistemic risk to trusted others.

Epistemic precarity

Participants’ daily lives were marked by what can be described as epistemic precarity—living with uncertainty not only about what information is accurate but also about how it will circulate and what relational consequences it may bring. As one woman put it: ‘Either we laugh at it, or it looks silly . . . but I’d still pass it on’. (CP23) Another described the emotional escalation that often follows misunderstandings: ‘They hear it differently, and suddenly it’s arguments’. (CP6) Conflicts between children often pulled adults into fraught exchanges: ‘The kids argue, the mothers deal with it, and suddenly there’s a fire on the roof’. (CP15) Residents described the stress of never knowing how far something would travel: ‘Sometimes I don’t even know who said it about me, but it’s already running’. (CP6)

Many participants expressed fear of being disbelieved or ridiculed. One said: ‘When I say something, they assume I’m lying’. (CP18) Another shared: ‘I’d rather not say anything so I don’t look stupid’. (CP11) These statements reveal how territorial stigma becomes internalised, shaping expectations of credibility and intensifying defensive silence. These dynamics illustrate environments with inadequate containment. Without institutional holding, neighbourhoods oscillate between support and emotional contagion.

Epistemic precarity here is not merely informational but relational and reputational. Knowing is risky because it exposes individuals to judgement, misrecognition, and conflict. Silence, selective sharing, or humour function as defensive adaptations to environments where credibility is fragile and easily undermined by stigma. These practices should be read as rational responses to chronic epistemic insecurity rather than disengagement.

Trust and the role of social workers

In contrast to distrust of institutions, social workers emerged consistently as trusted relational figures. Residents described turning to them not only for bureaucratic support but for emotional reassurance. ‘I always turn to the girls’, one participant said warmly (CP3). Another shared: ‘They explain it to me in a human way, not like at the office’. (CP6). Participants frequently sought help interpreting letters they feared to open alone: ‘When an email comes, I go to the social worker . . . I’m afraid to open it by myself’.

(CP9). Others emphasised the protective dimension of this support: ‘They know how to write it so it doesn’t cause trouble’. (CP11)

Institutional interactions evoked the opposite emotions. As one participant put it bluntly: ‘I don’t trust them . . . I don’t comment on anything’. (CP7) Another shared her frustration: ‘I tell them what is happening with the kids, and they still don’t believe me’. (CP9) These narratives reveal a pattern of testimonial injustice, where residents—especially women—feel systematically discredited in institutional encounters. In contrast, social workers functioned psychodynamically as containing figures: they absorbed anxiety, provided recognition and stabilised overwhelming information.

Disadvantaged neighbourhoods as psychosocial and epistemic ecosystems

Residents portrayed their neighbourhoods as emotionally dense and socially demanding environments, shaped by long-term disinvestment, territorial stigma and structural inequality. One woman said: ‘When I say where I’m from, it’s immediately bad’. (CP18). Another observed: ‘Nobody deals with anything here; everything is on us’. (CP6).

Rather than describing a simple absence of support, participants articulated a lived experience of being collectively responsible for managing crises, uncertainty, and everyday functioning. Help was expected to come primarily from within the neighbourhood, while external institutions were described as distant, slow, or selectively present—often intervening only once problems had escalated. This reinforced a shared understanding that coping, monitoring, and response were largely internal matters. Women carried significant epistemic and emotional responsibilities. One participant noted: ‘I monitor everything because no one else will do it’. (CP11). Another expressed frustration in not being believed: ‘I say it politely, and they act like I’m exaggerating’. (CP18). These responsibilities extended beyond individual households. Women described acting as informal information hubs—tracking school communication, welfare changes, and circulating rumours, while also deciding what information to pass on and what to withhold. This epistemic labour was experienced as continuous and high-stakes: missing or misinterpreting information could have immediate consequences for children, housing, or benefits.

Participants repeatedly framed this responsibility in terms of vigilance and blame. One woman stated: ‘You have to watch everything all the time. If you miss one thing, they say it’s your fault’. (CP11). Another emphasised the cumulative pressure of this role: ‘It never stops. School, offices, messages, people talking—there is always something you have to keep in your head’. (CP9). At the same time, participants highlighted the invisibility of this work. As one woman noted: ‘Nobody sees what we do every day. They only notice us when something goes wrong’. (CP9). Another added: ‘They think you’re careless, but they don’t see how much you’re actually trying to manage’. (CP18).

Residents also described a painful contradiction: ‘They monitor us everywhere, but when I need help, no one is there’. (CP3). This contradiction structured everyday interactions with institutions. Participants described frequent assessments, data collection, and expectations of compliance, alongside difficulties accessing timely explanations or meaningful assistance. Requests for clarification were sometimes interpreted as incompetence or resistance, reinforcing feelings of exposure and mistrust. As one woman explained: ‘When you ask again, they look at you like you’re

stupid, or like you're trying to cheat'. (CP18). Another participant described the asymmetry of these encounters: 'They ask and ask, they write everything down, but when I need an answer, there is nobody'. (CP3). As a result, institutional engagement was often approached cautiously, with information filtered and rehearsed before being shared (CP11). One participant described this strategy explicitly: 'You have to think carefully about what you say. If you say too much, it can be used against you'. (CP11).

Disadvantaged neighbourhoods operate as both containers and sources of psychic strain. They provide familiarity and shared struggle but also reproduce shame, vigilance and defensive withdrawal. Within this psychosocial ecology, information practices become emotional negotiations—ways of staying safe, preserving dignity and managing the anxieties of structural exclusion. Crucially, information here does not function as stable knowledge but as a relational resource—something to be managed carefully in order to avoid conflict, stigma, or institutional repercussions. Decisions about whether to speak, remain silent, verify, or pass information on are shaped less by abstract concerns about truth than by the anticipated relational and emotional consequences of knowing.

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight how digital exclusion in disadvantaged neighbourhoods is shaped not only by technological disparities but also by socio-spatial and relational processes. Digital engagement is embedded in histories of institutional mistrust, territorial stigma and structural disadvantage, aligning with relationship-based traditions in social work (Ruch, 2005).

A key insight is that digital exclusion is co-produced within systemic environments that presume digital competence yet fail to provide relational or emotional support. As digital divide research shows, disparities in access, skills and outcomes are socially patterned and intensified in digitalised welfare, schooling and health systems that assume users' interpretive capacity (Helsper, 2021; Liu, 2025; Nguyen et al., 2021; van Dijk, 2020). Communication through portals, automated notifications and email presupposes the ability to decode institutional language independently. For many participants, however, such interactions were confusing, intimidating and emotionally overwhelming, echoing research describing digital welfare systems as sites of anxiety, surveillance and potential sanction rather than support (Eubanks, 2018; Gillingham & Humphreys, 2010).

Within these conditions, residents confront a double bind: they are required to engage with digital interfaces that evoke fear or shame while receiving minimal relational holding. When systems become 'digital-first' without attending to emotional realities, the digital divide becomes both a symptom and mechanism of organisational exclusion. Welfare digitalisation intensifies emotional and epistemic burdens, particularly for women managing institutional communication. From a relational social work perspective, such organisational conditions undermine clients' capacity to think and act rather than enhancing autonomy (Cooper & Lousada, 2005; Ruch, 2005).

These findings underscore the importance of relational practice. Practitioners are called not only to provide information but to contain anxieties accompanying institutional interaction (Howe, 1995; Lanyado & Horne, 2009). Social workers were described as trusted figures who translated bureaucratic language, co-read threatening letters and stabilised affect, functioning as holding figures that enabled engagement with systems

that might otherwise induce shame or confusion (Hoggett, 2009; Hollway, 2013; Rustin, 2010).

Disadvantaged neighbourhoods emerge as psychosocial ecosystems shaped by territorial stigma, limited institutional presence and gendered care responsibilities. Residents internalise neighbourhood devaluation and anticipate dismissal in institutional encounters (Wacquant, 2007, 2008), shaping patterns of silence and self-monitoring. Women carry disproportionate epistemic and emotional labour in navigating schools, welfare agencies and digital platforms, frequently encountering testimonial injustice (Fricker, 2007).

Together, these dynamics contribute to what this study conceptualises as epistemic precarity: ongoing uncertainty about what information is trustworthy and how institutional messages should be interpreted. The digital divide thus appears less as inability to engage with technology than as an affective and relational response to surveillance, shame and institutional unpredictability, consistent with psychosocial accounts of digital marginality (Hargittai et al., 2018).

Taken together, these insights call for a psychosocial and relational conceptualisation of the digital divide. Digital engagement must be understood at the intersection of structural inequality, communal dynamics and organisational practice (Cooper & Lousada, 2005). From this perspective, digital inclusion requires more than devices or training: it calls for relational work that acknowledges the emotional meaning of technology and seeks to restore dignity and interpretive confidence. Social work therefore functions not only as service mediation but as epistemic and emotional care, enabling movement from avoidance towards trust and competence.

The findings can be situated within emerging debates on digital vulnerability, which conceptualise digitally mediated risk as layered and intersecting with broader processes of marginalisation (López Peláez & Marcuello-Servós, 2025). Rather than reducing digital exclusion to gaps in access or skills, digital vulnerability captures how economic precarity, welfare surveillance, debt enforcement and territorial stigma reinforce one another in digitally structured welfare systems. The anxiety, mistrust and reliance on mediating figures documented in disadvantaged neighbourhoods illustrate the relational and affective dimensions of this vulnerability. These insights have implications for the emerging field of digital social work (Goldkind & Wolf, 2015; Reamer, 2019), suggesting that professional training should move beyond technical competence towards inclusive, relationally attuned practice capable of addressing cumulative digital and social vulnerabilities.

Thus, the digital divide is revealed as a field in which social workers perform critical—and often invisible—labour. Relationship-based and organisationally aware social work practice is fundamental to enabling clients in disadvantaged neighbourhoods to navigate digital life with confidence, dignity and emotional safety.

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Lucie Průřová is a researcher in the field of social work whose work focuses on improving the quality and accessibility of social services. Her research pays particular attention to reducing barriers to service entry for people experiencing homelessness, especially those with lived experience of substance dependence.

Marek Mikulec is an Associate Professor in the field of social work whose research focuses on social exclusion, with particular attention to housing exclusion and housing insecurity. His work examines how structurally disadvantaged individuals and families navigate welfare systems, institutional encounters, and everyday life under conditions of housing precarity.

Ethics approval statement

The research was conducted in accordance with the Ethical Principles of Human Research, adopted by the American Psychological Association in 2016, and the applicable Czech laws. Informed consent to participate was written. The research was approved by the Ethics Committee of Faculty of Social Studies, University of Ostrava in 2025.

Financial interests

There are no financial interests or benefits that have arisen from the direct applications of this research.

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